

1 **HPV E2 activates Arhgap22.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 HPV E2 is the viral transcriptional activator but likely has a multitude of functions separate from the
7 E1-associated viral trans-activation event that remain undefined. We demonstrate here by ectopic
8 expression of HPV E2 in human cells and measurement of total transcription following next generation
9 RNA-sequencing activation of *Arhgap22* by human papillomavirus E2 protein.

10 Citations

11 1. Mori, M., Saito, K. and Ohta, Y., 2014. ARHGAP22 localizes at endosomes and regulates actin
12 cytoskeleton. PLoS One, 9(6), p.e100271.

13 2. Cheng, V.W., Vaughn-Beaucaire, P., Shaw, G.C., Kriegs, M., Droop, A., Psakis, G., Mittelbronn,
14 M., Humphries, M., Esteves, F., Hayes, J. and Cockle, J.V., 2025. ARHGAP12 and ARHGAP29 exert
15 distinct regulatory effects on switching between two cell morphological states through GSK-3 activity. *Cell*
16 *Reports*, 44(3).

17 GSE121627
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28